

DEFORMATION AND TEMPERATURE FIELDS IN SHORT FIBRE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Computational models using 1D Continuous Source Function Method (CSFM) along the fibre axis will be presented for simulation of displacement/stress/strain and temperature/heat flux in composites reinforced by short fibres with very large aspect ratio. CSFM is a meshless method reducing the problem considerably.

Keywords: Meshless method; large aspect ratio; linear elasticity; heat transfer

INTRODUCTION

Fibres are the most effective reinforcing material. Outstanding mechanical, thermal and electro-mechanical properties of Carbon Nano-Tubes (CNT), carbon fibres and some other fibres are well known. Composites Reinforced by Short Fibres/tubes (CRSF) are often defined to be materials of future with excellent electro-thermo-mechanical (ETM) properties. Understanding the behaviour of such composite materials is essential for structural design. Computational simulations play important role in this process. Strength, stiffness, thermal and electrical conduction of fibres are usually much larger than those of the matrix material. The aspect ratio of the short fibres is often $1:10^3$ - $1:10^6$, or even more. Because of these properties very large gradients are localized in all ETM fields along the fibres and in the matrix. These fields define the interaction of the fibres with the matrix, with the other fibres, with the boundaries of the domain/structure. Accurate computational simulation of the fields is important for correct assessment of the material behaviour.

Thousands or millions of fibres are often contained in a micro-dimension of such composite and its micro-structural properties are substituted by equivalent homogeneous continuum for macro dimensional simulations. If a matrix reinforced by Carbon Nano-Tubes (CNTs) having 1% volume of CNTs 1mm long and 20 nm diameter will contain 3.2×10^7 tubes and the CNTs can have general form (curvature, orientation) and can be randomly distributed, then the Control Volume Element for homogenisation would contain several hundred millions of CNTs for correct assessment homogenised properties such composite. In the simulations domain-type, boundary-type, mesh-free methodologies, or some combinations of different type methodologies can be used. Reduction techniques like the Fast Multi-pole (FM) methods were

developed in order to reduce models for far field interaction. The most effective method is the method which enables to obtain good accuracy with smallest computational effort.

In the simulations domain-type, boundary-type, mesh-free methodologies, or some combinations of different type methodologies can be used. In generally, the most effective method is the method which enables to obtain good accuracy with smallest computational effort.

The present methods mostly used to simulate the temperature fields in solids are:

- FEM and other volume discretization methods,
- BEM,
- Meshless and Mesh-reducing methods,
- Fast Multipole BIEM (Boundary Integral Equation Method). It is BEM for near field effects.

The main FEM and BEM disadvantage is very fine meshing to keep gradient and aspect ratio either in volume or in surface. BEM defines the problem by corresponding fundamental solution and leads to singular integral equations and full matrix after discretization. Because of large gradients and large aspect ratio of fibre surface, many boundary elements are necessary to solve the problem by required accuracy. Similar properties have also present formulations using meshless and mesh-reducing methods.

Figure 2 T-FEM mesh and detail on fibre end and BEM meshes [2]

Large finite elements are possible to be defined by Trefftz type formulation (T-FEM), which provides the considerable reduction of number of elements. In this formulation shape functions satisfy the governing equations in corresponding domain/subdomain. Figure 2 shows different mesh for T-FEM (FEM formulation) and BEM [2]. Commercial FEM package PROCISION [3] contains two types of T-elements: polynomial and nonpolynomial, stress concentration elements. The last one element properly reflects asymptotic behaviour of exact solution in the region of stress concentration. The solution is obtained by adaptive procedure by comparing the strain energy in computational steps and it is stopped when the change in the last two steps is smaller than 1%. The T-FE's can be much larger than classical FE's also for complicated shape of the element. The global and local (element) errors are evaluated from the sub-domain (element) boundary conditions. The accuracy of the element is

increased by increasing the order of the T-polynomials of the shape function and it can increase up to 12th order in the models. However, the inter-domain connection defined by polynomials smoothes out the gradients by large elements and so the interaction of the fibres [2].

Drastic reduction of the problem enables the Fast Multi-pole (FM) BEM [4] by which the kernel functions of boundary integrals are substituted by corresponding truncated Taylor series expansion and resulting discrete dipoles and moments are substituted for the continuum in far field interaction. However, classical BEM formulation describes the near field interaction and thus, the method is not as efficient as it is in the case of inhomogeneous materials when the aspect ratio of inclusions is small.

CONTINUOUS SOURCE FUNCTION METHOD

A meshless method has been developed [1] using 1D continuous source functions distributed along the fibre axis. The source functions are forces and their derivatives (dipoles and couples) for deformation field and temperature and temperature dipole (heat transfer). The intensities of the source functions are computed in order to satisfy the inter-domain boundary conditions in collocation points on the fibre boundaries. Such distribution enables to satisfy the boundary conditions with quite good accuracy both in longitudinal and circumferential directions of the fibre-matrix interface boundary for corresponding topology of composite.

The basic equation is derived from the boundary integral equation approach introducing a source function. In case of structural analysis, the source function is a unit force, in case of thermal analysis it is a unit heat source. The source functions produce fields of displacement, stress, temperature, heat flow in the elastic body (matrix). The derivative of source function in corresponding direction is called a dipole and is composed of two collinear forces acting in the opposite directions or a heat sink and a heat source acting at the same point.

The CSFM is a boundary meshless method reducing the problem considerably. The continuity conditions of temperature fields, expressed in collocation (discrete) points of the fibre-matrix interface, are used to compute intensities of continuous source functions of heat sources and heat dipoles located along the fibre axis. Because of large gradients in the intensities of source functions, the NURBS (Non-Uniform Rational B-Splines) were chosen to define the distribution. Number of unknown intensities is usually much smaller than the number of collocation points and the system of resulting equations is solved in the Least Square (LS) sense. Examples of computational simulations for single fibre in a matrix and regularly distributed fibres in a matrix are presented.

Fibres are assumed to be ideal conductors (at least in the first iteration step if such assumption is not accurate), and so, temperature in a fibre is taken to be constant. It is quite good approximation if the fibres are not too long and the heat conductivity of fibres is much greater than that of the matrix. These facts allow us to considerably simplify the mathematical model of the heat conduction in CRSF.

CSFM does not need any mesh. Continuity of temperature fields between the matrix and fibres is satisfied in discrete nodes – collocation points, only. Domain of solution is the matrix and the internal points of fibres are supposed to be outside this domain (i.e. inside the fibres). The source functions are continuously distributed along the fibre axis. They are defined by shape function and their intensities. The intensity of shape function

is modelled by 1D quadratic NURBS along the axis in order to satisfy boundary conditions (continuity of temperature between corresponding fibre and matrix).

Source functions

The source functions for thermal analysis are heat sources and heat dipoles. Heat source is scalar quantity. Heat dipole is a heat source and heat sink acting at the same point by approaching each other in some coordinate direction. Mathematically, it is a derivative of heat source in corresponding direction (i.e. the heat dipole is a vector). Heat sources and heat dipoles act in source points (mark by cross in Figure 3). They can be distributed discretely in source points or continuously. 1D distribution along fibre axis of the source functions is used in our models. Points marked by circles in the Figure 3 are collocation points and point denoted by square is an arbitrary point between the collocation points.

Temperature field by a unit heat source acting in arbitrary point of infinite domain is a fundamental solution and it is given by

$$T = \frac{1}{4\pi r} \quad (1)$$

where r is distance of the field point t and source point s , where the heat source is acting.

Figure 3 Discretely and continuously distributed source functions

Temperature field by a unit heat dipole in x_i direction is

$$T = \frac{1}{4\pi} \left(\frac{1}{r} \right)_{,i} = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{1}{r^2} r_{,i} = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{x_i}{r^3} \quad (2)$$

The index after comma denotes partial derivative in corresponding coordinate direction.

Heat flow in x_i direction is given by

$$q_i = -k \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_i} = -k T_{,i} = k \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{x_i}{r^3} \quad (3)$$

where k is coefficient of heat conductivity of the matrix. The material of fibre is considered to be ideal conductor, i.e. its coefficient of conductivity is many orders better

than that of the matrix. Usually the heat conductivity of fibres is much larger than that of the matrix. If the fibres are unidirectional oriented in the matrix, they improve the conductivity of the composite material in fibre direction, i. e. the material can be good conductor in the fibre direction and good isolator in perpendicular direction to the fibres.

Heat flow through a surface with the normal n is defined as

$$q_n = q_i n_i \quad (4)$$

The total contribution of the source functions to the temperature and heat flow in corresponding collocation point is given by integrals along all source function paths (fibre axes). Because of finite thickness of the fibre the integrals are quasi-singular with corresponding weak or strong singularities. Of course the closest points will influence the fields more than the far points.

The integration can be made analytically [1] or numerically. The analytical integration is possible for straight fibres, but the integral kernels are more complicated if the fibres are curved and numerical integration is necessary. After numerical experiments on behaviour of source functions in composite material and about their influence to physical fields following rules were chosen for generation of collocation points and numerical integration:

- Collocation points are necessary to be chosen denser at the ends of fibres and by the points nearest to the ends of closest fibres.
- Because of very large differences in denominator (distance between source and collocation points) the whole integration path is split into integration elements. In our models the smallest element (closest to the collocation point) have to be equal to the fibre diameter and the others are about as large as the distance of its closest point from the collocation point. In this way same number of Gauss integration points can be used for all elements with about equal error from all integration elements in the model.

CSFM Model

If it is assumed that the thermal conductivity of fibres is by several orders larger than that of matrix material then the temperature of the fibre can be considered to be constant.

Figure 4 Distribution of source functions and collocation points

Heat sources and dipoles 1D-continuously distributed along the fibre axis are used to simulate the interactions of fibres with the matrix and with other fibres. Collocation points are located on the interface fibre-matrix. The continuity of temperature is satisfied in the collocation points. Integration elements are along fibre axis.

NURBS shape functions

The distribution of source functions is 1D. The 1D elements use quadratic NURBS shape functions [5], [6], [7]. The NURBS curve is defined by its order, set of weighted control points and knot vector. NURBS curve takes form (5), where fractional part can be denoted as rational basis function.

$$C(u) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k N_{i,n} w_i \mathbf{P}_i}{\sum_{j=1}^k N_{j,n} w_j} \quad (5)$$

where k is number of control points \mathbf{P}_i , u is parameter (in our case it is linear dimension in fibre direction), $N_{i,n}$ is the basis function of i -th control point and degree n (quadratic NURBS are used in our model) and w_i are weights corresponding to the control point.

The denominator is a normalizing factor equal to one if all weights are taken equal to one. This can be seen from the partition of unity property of basis functions. The equation (5) can be rewritten as:

$$C(u) = \sum_{i=1}^k R_{i,n} \mathbf{P}_i \quad (6)$$

where the fraction in (1) is marked as $R_{i,n}$. $R_{i,n}$ are the rational basis functions.

The order of a NURBS curve defines the number of nearby points that influence any given point on the curve. The curve is represented mathematically by a polynomial of degree one less than order of the curve. Hence, second-order curve (which are represented by linear polynomials) are called linear curves, third-order curves are called quadratic. The number of control points must be greater than or equal to the order of the curve.

The positions of set of control points determine the shape of the curve (Figure 6). The change by moving one control point allows making localized changes without affecting the overall shape of the curve. Each control point influences the part of the curve nearest to it but little or no effect on parts of the curve that are farther away. Each point of the curve is computed by taking a weighted sum of a number of control points. The weight of each point varies according to the governing parameter. For a curve of degree n , the weight of any control point is only nonzero in $n+1$ intervals of the parameter space. At the boundaries of intervals, the basis functions go smoothly to zero.

The knot vector is a sequence of parameter values that determines where and how the control points affect the NURBS curve. The points demarcating the intervals are known as knot points. The ordered list of knot is knot vector. The number of knots is always equal to number of control points plus curve degree plus one. The knot vector divides the parametric space in the intervals. Values in the knot vector should be in non-descending order. The knot vector for basis functions in the Figure 4 is (1.5, 1.5, 1.5, 2,

3, 4, 4.5, 5.5, 5.5, 5.5). To control exact placement of the endpoints of curve, we use multiple identical knots. Notice, that basis function $N_{4,3}$ associated with control point B_4 have larger value as $N_{1,3}$, $N_{2,3}$, $N_{3,3}$ and $N_{5,3}$ and NURBS curve would be pulled towards control point B_4 . At $u=1.5$, all the basis functions except $N_{0,3}$ have value 0, so control point B_0 is the only one to effect the curve and thus the curve coincides with that control point. Each control point has its own basis function.

Basis functions $N_{i,n}$ are computed as:

$$N_{i,n} = f_{i,n}N_{i,n-1} + g_{i+1,n}N_{i+1,n-1} \quad (7)$$

We can write the functions f and g as:

$$f_{i,n}(u) = \frac{u - k_i}{k_{i+n} - k_i} \quad \text{and} \quad g_{i,n}(u) = \frac{k_{i+n} - u}{k_{i+n} - k_i} \quad (8)$$

The sum of basis functions for particular value of the parameter is unity. It is partition of unity property of basis function as we can see in the Figure 5.

Figure 5 NonUniform basis functions for a curve with multiple identical knots at the beginning and end

Figure 6 illustrates influence of $x(u)$ and $y(u)$ on smoothness of approximated curve. The smoothness is decreased or increased by shifting the $x(u)$ and by $y(u)$ values, respectively. Such shifting of values can be caused e.g. by errors, position of ends of integration elements, heat source intensity value, etc.

Figure 7 documents definition of 3D curve by control points and corresponding NURBS shape functions. This can be conveniently used for definition random curved fibres in a matrix.

Figure 6 Influence of $x(u)$ and $y(u)$ on smoothness

Figure 7 Modification of NURBS 3D curve through the control points (circles)

EXAMPLES

The first two examples are computational results for temperature fields in a material containing single fibre with ideal heat conductivity. Length of the fibre is 100 times larger than its radius in the Figure 8 and 1000 times larger than the radius in the Figure 9.

On the left part of Figure 8, there is heat source intensity along the single fibre (z-direction is direction of fibre axis). After integration of intensity of heat sources, we obtain heat flow along axis in the single fibre. The maximum heat flow is in the middle of the fibre.

Figure 9 shows the largest heat flow in the ends of fibre through the fibre surface, i.e. in perpendicular direction to the fibre axis. In these parts are also the largest temperature gradients.

Figure 8 Heat source intensity (left) and heat flow along single fibre (L=100R) in matrix in axis direction

Figure 9 Heat flow through the fibre surface along the fibre axis (L=1000R) on single fibre in matrix material

Figure 10 Patch of overlapping and non-overlapping rows of fibres

The models can involve not only one fibre but also patch of fibres which are straight and distributed regularly. The patches of fibres in the next example (Fig. 10) consist of overlapping and non-overlapping rows of fibres. One can see the strong interaction between fibres in case of overlapping fibres. This is very different from the case of non-overlapping rows of fibres.

Figure 11 Heat source intensity and heat flow in fibres ($L=1000R$) without overlap (black, green), with smaller 16R (blue) and larger 160R (red) gap

Figure 11 illustrates heat source intensity and heat flow in fibre with and without overlap. The aspect ratio of fibres is 1:500 (fibre diameter: fibre length, R is radius, L is length). Black and green curves are for non-overlapping fibres with smaller and larger gap in fibre direction. The overlapped fibres show the different contribution to heat transmission. Blue curve presents smaller gap and red line larger one. One can see that the fibres without overlap transmit more heat in the case of larger gap between the rows of fibres. It is because of larger difference of temperatures in the points connecting the ends of fibres. Similar behaviour introduces also the patches with overlap.

Figure 12 Heat source intensity and heat flow in fibre direction ($L=100R$) without overlap (black, green), with smaller 2R (blue) and larger 16R (red) gap

Comparing the cases with or without overlap, the fibres with overlap transmit much more heat and the ends of fibres interact very strongly with the nearest fibres. Notice large gradients in heat source intensities on the ends of fibres and also in the points closest to the ends of neighbour fibres. These parts require very fine distribution of control points for definition of shape functions in order to keep good accuracy and numerical stability of the models.

The similar behaviour of patches of fibres is documented also in the Figure 12 presented results of fibres with and without overlap of fibres with aspect ratio 1:50 (shorter fibres than previous). Different distribution of fibres and corresponding colours are defined in the figure. The smaller gap (2R - blue) in perpendicular direction to fibre axis results in higher percentage of fibres in the volume and larger heat flow and thus better conductivity in the fibre direction. Stronger interaction between ends of fibres is evident by smaller gap between fibres in the fibre direction in both heat source intensity and in heat flow in the fibre. The waviness in the end parts (black) and in the middle part (blue) is caused by numerical instability of the model. The accuracy is not influenced much by this effect, however.

CONCLUSIONS

Presented computational model enable to simulate interaction of fibres with matrix and with other fibres. Very different material properties of fibres and matrix evoke large gradients of the physical fields in matrix along the fibre as well as in perpendicular direction to the fibre axis. Correct simulation is important for assessment of properties of the composite. Because of the large aspect ratio the interactions in perpendicular direction to fibre axis are stronger and a fibre influence is at larger distance. A fibre can transmit large amount of load or heat comparing to particles with small aspect ratio. Fibres with large aspect ratio are much stiffer in axial direction than in bending, however, axial stresses in the fibres can be even by several orders larger than stresses in the matrix. More discussion on computational simulations and results will be presented.

The Method of Continuous Source Functions is a boundary meshless method using collocation technique. It provides good accuracy even for large aspect ratio of fibres. Continuous heat source and dipole models enable to simulate both near and far fields in materials reinforced by fibres and they introduce large reduction of models. Correct simulation of the far fields is necessary for evaluation of homogenization process in multi-level modelling. Similar accuracy can be obtained by other methods like BEM or FEM when the number of elements is by several orders larger than in presented method (see [2] for the comparison of the methods). One can imagine how many boundary elements are necessary for one only fibre if the aspect ratio is 1:10000 by comparing with the models given in the Fig. 2 (error checks [2] have shown that required error level was satisfied by the middle model).

The presented model assumes ideal conductivity of the fibre. As the heat flow in fibre can exceed the largest heat flow in the matrix by several orders, if the aspect ratio of fibres is large, the assumption of ideal conductivity can be incorrect, however, iterative corrections can improve the accuracy in very few steps (usually not more than 4 steps are necessary to obtain final solution).

Correct simulation of the interaction of fibres is important for evaluation of composite properties. The high gradients in the fields require some experience with choose of control points for definition of the continuous source functions along the fibre axis.

Our next aims are: Further reduction of models (iterative solutions) and multilevel models and modelling of imperfect straight and curved fibres in order to be able to simulate more complicated micro-structure of such composite materials.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Support of the DSSI, grant agencies APVV (grant No. APVT-20-035404) and RTO-NATO (grant No. 001-AVT-SVK) and VEGA (grant No. 1/0140/08) for this research is gratefully acknowledged.

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